

AN AUTOMATED HF
NOISE MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract

The determination and control of man-made noise in the 2MHz - 32 MHz (HF) frequency band is a major concern to those who must operate, maintain, and plan for HF receiver installations. The ability to obtain an accurate and statistically significant characterization of the RF noise throughout the entire HF spectrum and not be limited to a set of noise measurements taken at several preselected points within the spectrum is paramount. This paper describes an automated noise measurement system, configured entirely with off the shelf components, that accurately gathers a representative sample of both noise and signal data over the entire HF spectrum. The measurement system described, although not strictly portable, has been taken literally around the world, via commercial air carriers, to gather noise data. The results of two surveys, one conducted in a quiet rural area and the other conducted in a suburban area are also presented.

Introduction

Radio noise in the 2-32 MHz frequency range can be characterized as being composed of naturally occurring and man-made noise sources. Variation in either of these two components of RF noise could result in the degradation of a receiver site and possibly result in the site becoming marginal or unusable.

Naturally occurring noise is either atmospheric or galactic. The primary source of atmospheric noise is thunderstorm activity. Galactic noise sources are extraterrestrial such as the sun and other stars. Since naturally occurring noise is very temporal and not controllable, very little can be done to limit/alter its effect on a receiver site.

Man-made noise has been and will continue to be a problem for receiver sites around the world. Man-made noise sources may be classified as follows:

- (1) Incidental Radiators: Electric power lines, ignition systems, electric motors, home electrical appliances.
- (2) Intentional Radiators: Wireless announcing systems, campus radio stations, walkie-talkies, door-opener transmitters and most importantly licensed transmitters.
- (3) Unintentional Radiators: Cable TV systems, microwave ovens, industrial heaters, medical diathermy equipment, RF-stabilized arc welders and many others.

Since the RF noise environment is composed of contributions from all three of the man-made noise sources as well as the natural noise sources, the RF noise will vary both spatially and temporally. Any residential or commercial development in the vicinity of an existing or proposed receiver site will result in an increase in the man-made component of the RF noise. The Joint Technical Advisory Committee of the IEEE has adopted the following area classification categories for frequencies less than 10 MHz [1]:

- (1) URBAN - Business areas of cities with populations over 200,000 (e.g., New York City, Baltimore, Denver), including the heavy industrial area of all cities. Closely spaced buildings of 10 stories and higher and industries such as auto manufacturing facilities or harbor installations are included in this category.
- (2) SUBURBAN - Residential areas of large cities (e.g., Baltimore, Washington, DC) and entire cities of less than 50,000 population with light industry. This classification extends to remote areas in the proximity of heavy power transmission and consumption, such as areas adjacent to high voltage transmission lines or those near lumber or mining operations.
- (3) RURAL - Areas in which residences are spaced an average of over one mile apart and locations which are more than one mile from high-voltage power lines.

Schultz, Spaulding and Barghausen [2] added a fourth category, QUIET RURAL, for locations that are several kilometers from any man-made noise emitters. The noise level for this is the same as those given for quiet receiving locations by the CCIR [3].

Above 20 MHz man-made noise correlates closely with motor vehicle traffic density [4,5,6]. Because of this the classification scheme must take traffic density into account. URBAN areas must include locations of congested vehicle traffic. SUBURBAN should include areas of moderate to heavy uncongested traffic and RURAL areas are those locations near lightly traveled roads.

The Naval Electronics Systems Engineering Center in Charleston, SC as the engineering agent for the U.S. Navy's shore Electromagnetic Environmental Effects (E3) program has been tasked to determine the HF noise environment at both existing and proposed HF receiver sites. In response to this requirement and utilizing the aforementioned criteria, NAVEXLEX Charleston has developed the automated HF noise measurement system described in this paper.

NOISE DATA COLLECTION SYSTEM

The developed automated noise data collection system is configured utilizing the following equipment (see figure 1):

1. Hewlett Packard model 8566 Spectrum Analyzer.
2. Hewlett Packard model 9836 Desktop Computer.
3. Hewlett Packard model 461A Preamplifier.
4. Antenna Research Associates ODC-100 Antenna.
5. Various coaxial cables with measured loss.

The noise measurement techniques currently in use rely on data gathered in "quiet areas" in the vicinity of a limited number of specific frequencies within the band of interest (usually 5 to 7 specific frequencies within the HF band are selected). The developed automated noise data collection system utilizes the computer controlled spectrum analyzer to gather both noise and signal data throughout the entire HF band. The noise data collection algorithm divides the 2 - 32 MHz frequency band into 100 bands (each 300 kHz wide). Each of the 300 kHz bands is sampled by sliding a 3 kHz window across the band. The signal data algorithm divides the 2 - 32 MHz frequency band into 10 bands (each 3 MHz wide). Each of the 3 MHz bands is also sampled by sliding a 3 kHz window across the band.

Both noise and signal data are gathered on an hourly basis. Forty five (45) complete cycles are made through the 100 noise bands and the 10 signal bands every hour. The data collection process begins on the hour with the collection of noise data. A sweep is made through each of the 100 noise frequency bands. After each of the 100 sweeps is completed, the minimum value within that band is stored. Each stored noise value is the RMS noise in a 1 Hz bandwidth. Since there are 45 cycles/hour, there will be 45 samples for each of the 100 frequency bands stored every hour (i.e. 4,500 noise samples/hour, 108,000/day and 756,000/week). After each noise cycle is completed, all 100 bands, a signal cycle is initiated. During the signal cycle, a sweep is made through each of the 10 frequency bands. At the completion of each signal cycle all 1000 data points within the 3 MHz signal band are stored. The units for the signal data are $\text{dB}\mu\text{volts}$, 3 KHz bandwidth and a reference level of $140 \text{ dB}\mu\text{volts}$. With 10 signal bands and 45 cycles/hour, the system will gather and store 450,000 signal samples/hour, 10,800,000/day and 75,600,000/week.

It will not take a complete hour to make 45 cycles through the 100 noise bands and the 10 signal bands. During the remaining time within each hour, the recorded noise data and signal data are transferred to the system's internal disks. Any remaining time within the hour will cause the system to go into an idle mode. At the start of the next hour, the cycle will repeat. The system idle mode usually lasts from 3 to 5 minutes. The system, as presently configured, requires that the data disks be replaced once every 24 hours.

DATA ANALYSIS

The described system has been utilized to gather HF noise data at a number of locations throughout the world. Once the data has been gathered in the field, it is taken back to the home office for analysis. The types of analyses that are currently available are listed below.

1. Amplitude probability distribution (APD).
2. Confidence Intervals
3. Amplitude vs time vs frequency
4. Amplitude vs frequency vs time
(All noise results are presented in terms of the external noise figure, F_a , in units of dBkT_0 .)

The APD results presented in figures 3 through 10 are results from surveys conducted in a suburban area and in a quiet rural area. The data collected compares very favorably with the median external noise figure (F_n) data for urban, suburban, rural and quiet rural areas [7]. For comparison, the median F_n curves (see figure 2) are superimposed on the APD results.

SUMMARY

The system presented accurately collects large amounts of both noise and signal data throughout the entire HF spectrum. Other techniques in current use gather only noise data and gather this data at a limited number of points within the HF band. The system described is completely automated and requires very little user intervention. It is configured completely with off the shelf equipment. The data analysis software gives the user great flexibility in analysing the data.

Figure 3 APD Suburban Area 0000-0500 Hours

Figure 4 APD Suburban Area 0600-1100 Hours

Figure 5 APD Suburban Area 1200-1700 Hours

Figure 6 APD Suburban Area 1800-2300 Hours

Figure 7 APD Quiet Rural Area 0000-0500 Hours

Figure 8 APD Quiet Rural Area 0600-1100 Hours

Figure 9 APD Quiet Rural Area 1200-1700 Hours

Figure 10 APD Quiet Rural Area 1800-2300 Hours